

Mixed Ligand Chelates of *N*-Phosphonomethyl Glycine

RAMESH PANGUNOORI and KASHI RAM*

Department of Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007

Manuscript received 17 August 1993, revised 6 December 1993, accepted 29 December 1993

The formation constants of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 binary ($[M-A]$ and $[M-A_2]$) and 1 : 1 : 1 ternary metal chelates ($[M-A-L]$ or $[M-L'-A]$, where A = *N*-phosphonomethyl glycine (NPMG), L = glycine (Gly) and β -alanine (Ala), L' = 5-sulphosalicylic acid (5-SSA), oxalic acid (Oxa), 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen), 2,2'-bipyridyl (Bipy) and iminodiacetic acid (Imda) and M = Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}) have been determined potentiometrically in aqueous medium at 20, 30, 40 and 50° and at 0.10 M (KNO_3) ionic strength. NPMG behaves as a primary ligand in presence of N,O donors, Gly and Ala and as a secondary ligand in presence of O,O and N,N donors, 5-SSA, Oxa, Phen, Bipy and imda. The stepwise and overall 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 : 1 stability constants, $\log K_1$ (or $\log K'_1$), $\log K_2$, $\log \beta_2$, $\log K_T$, or $\log K'_T$, the differences in stability constants of 1 : 1 secondary metal complexes and 1 : 1 : 1 ternary systems ($\Delta \log K$ or $\Delta \log K'$), the percentage of relative stabilisation values and percentages of distribution of various species have been evaluated and discussed in terms of the basicity of ligands, statistical aspects, electrostatic interaction, metal-ligand π -interaction, denticity, nature of donor sites and stereochemical aspects. Thermodynamic parameters of the binary and ternary systems have been determined and discussed.

N-Phosphonomethyl glycine (NPMG) is a potential herbicide and its chemistry has immense importance in the fields of agriculture, industry and medicine. The bivalent metal ions affect the NPMG uptake and transport efficiency in plants. This is due to the formation of stable low mobile complexes¹. The bivalent metal ions have the great control on the herbicidal activity of NPMG². It inhibits the metal corrosion by complexing with the metal ions³ and its important application is in the use of radio nucleide complexes for bone scintigraphy⁴.

Literature survey shows that excepting a few papers on binary systems^{5,6}, no work has been done on NPMG with different metal ions and in different systems. The active role of metal ions in the applications of NPMG has become the driving force for us to study the interaction of metal ions such as Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with NPMG and in its combination with some other O,O, N,N and N,O donor ligands such as 5-sulphosalicylic acid (5-SSA), oxalic acid (Oxa), 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen), 2,2'-bipyridyl (Bipy), glycine (Gly), β -alanine (Ala) and iminodiacetic acid (Imda).

Results and Discussion

The n values ($0.1 < n < 1.9$) for $[M-A]$

and $[M-A_2]$ systems indicate the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal complexes. The ligand NPMG starts coordinating M^{II} ions in the pH range of 5.0–5.5. The metal-ligand formation constants have been evaluated by various computational techniques, viz. half-integral method, pointwise calculation and least-squares measurements. The average $\log K_n$ values for all the binary systems are presented in Table 1. The standard deviations were found to be less than ± 0.05 log units.

In the ternary systems studied, the mixed ligand $[M-L'-A]$ curves closely follow those of the 1 : 1 $[M-L']$ binary curves in all the systems except in the systems where Gly and Ala are used; in these latter systems the mixed ligand $[M-A-L]$ curves closely follow those of the 1 : 1 $[M-A]$ binary curves. The mixed-ligand curves follow the binary curves in the lower pH region (pH 3.5) until the protons of primary ligands are neutralised indicating the formation of binary $[M-L']$ or $[M-A]$ complexes and non-coordination of A or L with M^{II} ions in this region. The divergence of the ternary $[M-L'-A]$ or $[M-A-L]$ curves from the binary systems above this region reveals the formation of ternary complexes in two-steps equilibria. This is further supported by the non-su-

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE FORMATION OF 1 : 1 AND 1 : 2 METAL CHELATES OF *N*-PHOSPHONOMETHYL GLYCINETemp. = 30°, Ionic strength = 0.10 M (KNO₃)

Metal ion	Stability constants	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS° J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_r^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H_r^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS_r° J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
H ⁺	pK ₁	5.36	—	—	—	—	—
	pK ₂	9.75	—	—	—	—	—
Co ^{II}	log K ₁	11.20	65	48	57	—	—
	log K ₂	8.55	50	37	42	—	—
	log β ₂	19.75	115	61	178	—	—
	log K ₁ ²	—	—	—	—	15	11
Ni ^{II}	log K ₁	11.61	67	52	52	—	—
	log K ₂	8.70	50	40	34	—	—
	log β ₂	20.31	118	62	184	—	—
	log K ₁ ²	—	—	—	—	17	11
Cu ^{II}	log K ₁	13.50	78	65	44	—	—
	log K ₂	9.05	53	46	22	—	—
	log β ₂	22.55	131	73	192	—	—
	log K ₁ ²	—	—	—	—	26	19

perimposable nature of the theoretical composite curves in the region of mixed-ligand complex formation⁷.

The metal-ligand stability constants of ternary complexes log K_T¹ or log K_T² alongwith other related parameters, viz. Δlog K and '% relative stabilisation', [(%) R.S. = (log K_T¹ - log K₁) × 100 / log K₁] (Table 2) are used for a quantitative estimation of the relative stabilisation of these ternary systems at a given temperature and ionic strength⁸. Larger negative values indicate lesser stabilisation of the ternary complexes.

From a knowledge of proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants, the distribution of the total metal among the various metal-ligand species as a function of pH is calculated by a computer program BEST due to Martell and Motekaitis⁹. As a representative case, the distribution diagram of Cu^{II}-NPMG-Gly system is given in Fig. 1. This and all other diagrams reveal that formation of ternary complexes occur in a stepwise manner.

Lowering of stabilities of ternary complexes compared to that of binary chelates may be due to the greater destabilisation effect^{7,10} caused by the ligand repulsion in the mixed ligand complexes than that in the binary systems, coupled with the availability of lesser number of coordination

Fig. 1. Distribution diagram for Cu^{II}-NPMG-Gly system.

sites for the second ligand on the primary complexes [M-L'] compared to free M^{II} (aq) ion¹¹. A comparison of these statistical considerations reveal that the order of stability of ternary complexes with respect to the other ligands L or L' (L = Gly and Ala; L' = 5-SSA, Oxa, Phen, Bipy and imda) in terms of donor atoms is found to be O,O > N,N > N,O, i.e. 5-SSA > Oxa > Phen > Bipy > Gly < Ala < imda. This is in accordance with their basicity order and denticity nature, because for a series of similar ligands the higher the basicity of the ligand, the greater is the stability of metal complex¹⁰. Electrostatic attractions between primary complex [M-L'] and the secondary ligand (A) also facilitates the formation of ternary complexes.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS AND PERCENTAGE OF RELATIVE STABILISATION VALUES OF TERNARY METAL CHELATES OF *N*-PHOSPHONOMETHYL GLYCINE WITH VARIOUS OTHER N,O, O,O AND N,N DONOR LIGANDS

Temp = 30°, Ionic strength = 0.10 M (KNO₃)

Ternary system	Co ^{II}			Ni ^{II}			Cu ^{II}		
	Stability constant	$\Delta \log K = [\log K_T - \log K_T^1]$ (-ve)	(%) R S (-ve)	Stability constant	$\Delta \log K = [\log K_T - \log K_T^1]$ (-ve)	(%) R S (-ve)	Stability constant	$\Delta \log K = [\log K_T - \log K_T^1]$ (-ve)	(%) R S (-ve)
	$\log K_T$	$\log K_T^1$		$\log K_T$	$\log K_T^1$		$\log K_T$	$\log K_T^1$	
NPMG-Gly	3.20	1.50	31.91	4.00	1.65	29.20	5.30	2.64	33.24
NPMG-Ala	3.92	0.08	1.70	5.00	0.20	3.84	5.70	1.40	19.71
	Stability constant	$\Delta \log K' = [\log K_T' - \log K_1]$ (-ve)	(%) R S (-ve)	Stability constant	$\Delta \log K' = [\log K_T' - \log K_1]$ (-ve)	(%) R S (-ve)	Stability constant	$\Delta \log K' = [\log K_T' - \log K_1]$ (-ve)	(%) R S (-ve)
	$\log K_T'$	$\log K_1$		$\log K_T'$	$\log K_1$		$\log K_T'$	$\log K_1$	
5-SSA-NPMG	9.28	1.92	17.14	9.96	1.65	14.21	12.59	0.91	6.74
Oxa-NPMG	8.36	2.84	25.33	8.55	3.06	26.35	10.36	3.14	23.25
Phen-NPMG	8.03	3.17	28.30	9.29	2.32	19.98	11.81	1.69	12.51
Bipy-NPMG	8.10	3.10	27.67	8.53	3.08	26.52	9.77	3.73	27.62
imda-NPMG	9.61	1.59	14.19	10.68	0.93	8.01	13.45	0.05	0.37

Analysis of $\log K_n$ into their component heat and entropy terms is essential to the fully understanding of the factors such as size, shape, electronic structure of the central metal ion and the ligand, the temperature and the composition of the solvents, which influence the stability of a metal complex¹².

In the present work the proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants have been calculated at four different temperatures, i.e. 20, 30, 40 and 50° and at a constant ionic strength of 0.10 M (KNO₃). There is a regular decrease in the values of proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants with increasing temperature. The values of ΔG° accompanying the metal-ligand complex

forming relations were calculated at 30°, those of ΔH° calculated from the linear plots of $\log K_n$ vs $1/T$ according to the equation of an iso-baric reaction¹³, and the ΔS° values were calculated from the values of ΔH° and ΔG° .

The values of ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° for binary systems of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal ions with NPMG and for ternary systems of Cu^{II} metal ion with NPMG and Gly, Ala, 5-SSA, Oxa, Phen, Bipy and imda, are presented in Tables 1 and 3 respectively. The chelates of these ligands are all formed spontaneously as evidenced by the negative values of ΔG° . The decrease in metal ion stability constants of these chelates with increase in temperature and negative values

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AND THEIR ELECTROSTATIC AND CRATIC COMPONENTS FOR THE TERNARY SYSTEMS OF Cu^{II} WITH NPMG AND OTHER LIGANDS

Temp = 30°, Ionic strength = 0.10 M (KNO₃)

Ternary system	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS° J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_c^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH_c° kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_e^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H_e^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹
NPMG-Gly	31	19	40	16	6	25	24
NPMG-Ala	33	19	47	18	7	26	25
5-SSA-NPMG	73	49	79	25	10	59	58
Oxa-NPMG	60	41	64	21	8	49	48
Phen-NPMG	69	48	68	22	9	57	56
Bipy-NPMG	57	32	82	25	10	42	41
imda-NPMG	78	55	76	24	9	65	64

of ΔH° indicate that the reactions are exothermic in nature. This probably results from the covalent interaction of metal ion and nitrogen atom of the amino acid group in NPMG. The positive values of ΔS° and a much greater increase in the number of particles during the reaction lead to disorderness in the system favouring the chelate formation.

The log K_1 values for all the *d*-block metal chelates studied were found to be higher than those of log K_2 values indicating that the 1:1 chelates are energetically more favoured over the 1 : 2 chelates. As pointed out by PoI and Nancollas¹⁴ that if the 1 : 1 chelate is more likely, then even 1:2 chelate formed reacts with a free metal ion to form 1:1 chelate and the thermodynamic parameters are calculated by using the relationships,

$$\Delta G_r^\circ = \Delta G_1^\circ - \Delta G_2^\circ \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta H_r^\circ = \Delta H_1^\circ - \Delta H_2^\circ \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta S_r^\circ = \Delta S_1^\circ - \Delta S_2^\circ \quad (3)$$

where ΔG_r° , ΔH_r° and ΔS_r° are the thermodynamic parameters for the formation of 1 : 1 chelates from the free metal ion and 1 : 2 chelates. The ΔG_r° and ΔH_r° values were found to be negative while ΔS_r° values positive (Table 1), from which it could be concluded that the mono-complex formation is highly favoured over the bis-complex formation.

To get an insight into the extent of ionic and covalent nature of the binary and ternary complexes formed, the ΔG° and ΔH° values have

been separated into their respective electrostatic (ΔG_e° , ΔH_e°) and cratic (ΔG_c° , ΔH_c°) components as described by Degischer and Nancollas¹⁵. The electrostatic components of ΔG° and ΔH° were calculated from the equations,

$$\Delta G_e^\circ = -\nu (\Delta S^\circ + R \Delta n \ln 55.5) \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta H_e^\circ = (T-\nu) (\Delta S^\circ + R \Delta n \ln 55.5) \quad (5)$$

where ν represents a temperature characteristic of the medium (ν for aqueous medium is 218 K), Δn stands for the change in the number of solute particles when the reactants change to products. The cratic components were obtained from equations,

$$\Delta G_c^\circ = \Delta G^\circ - \Delta G_e^\circ - \Delta n RT \ln 55.5 \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta H_c^\circ = \Delta H^\circ + \Delta H_e^\circ \quad (7)$$

Comparison of the electrostatic and cratic parts of the thermodynamic parameters (Table 4) for the equilibrium,

indicates that the values of ΔG_c° are significantly more negative than the ΔG_e° suggesting that cratic forces are stronger than the electrostatic forces in 1 : 1 chelates. The difference between the two components decrease in the order : $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$, which indicates that the ionic character and number of unpaired electrons increase in the reverse order : $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$. Thermodynamic data (Table 1) computed for the equilibrium,

TABLE 4—ELECTROSTATIC AND CRATIC COMPONENTS OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE FORMATION OF 1 : 1 AND 1 : 2 METAL CHELATES OF NPMG*

Temp = 30°, Ionic strength = 0.10 M (KNO₃)

Metal

ion	1 : 1 Complex				1 : 2 Complex			
	$-\Delta G_e^\circ$	$-\Delta H_e^\circ$	$-\Delta G_c^\circ$	$-\Delta H_c^\circ$	$-\Delta G_e^\circ$	$-\Delta H_e^\circ$	$-\Delta G_c^\circ$	$-\Delta H_c^\circ$
Co ^{II}	20	8	56	55	17	6	43	42
Ni ^{II}	19	7	59	58	15	6	46	45
Cu ^{II}	17	7	72	71	12	5	51	50

*Values in kJ mol⁻¹.

show a decrease in the ionic and covalent characteristics indicating again that bis-complexes are less stable than mono-complexes. In ternary systems cratic components are larger than their corresponding electrostatic components favouring their formation in solutions.

Experimental

The ligand NPMG was synthesised by known procedure¹⁶. All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The general experimental procedures were similar to those described elsewhere^{17,18}. The proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants of binary systems were determined potentiometrically in aqueous medium and the values of π_A , pk_1 , pk_2 , π , pL , $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated by Irving-Rossotti titration technique¹⁹ and checked by Martell and Chaberek method²⁰. The formation constants of ternary complexes were determined by using the method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa²¹. For calculating the thermodynamic parameters of binary systems of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and of ternary systems of Cu^{II} with NPMG, experiments were carried out at 20, 30, 40 and 50°.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. M. G. Ram Reddy, Principal, U.C.S., Osmania University, for his constant encouragement and Prof. P. K. Sai Prakash, Head, Department of Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad, for facilities.

References

1. L. V. DOLINSKAYA, A. M. MAKEEV and D. I. CHKANIKOV, *Fiziol. Biokhim. Kul't Rast.*, 1989, **21**, 70 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1989, **111**, 148741).
2. V. SUBRAMANIAM and E. PATRICK, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1988, **36**, 1326.
3. Y. I. KUZNETSOV and T. I. BARDASHEVA, *Zusch. Met.*, 1988, **24**, 234 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **108**, 194685).
4. V. I. LEVIN, V. V. SEDOV, I. N. TRONOVA, L. P. STAROVOITOVA, G. E. KODINA, N. P. GROMOVA, N. M. DYATLOVA and M. V. RUDOMINO, *Otkrytiya Izobert* 1985, **29**, 262.
5. H. E. LUNDAGER MADSEN, H. H. CHRISTENSEN and C. G. PETERSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand., Ser. A*, 1978, **32**, 79 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **88**, 142427).
6. R. J. MOTEKAITIS and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1985, **14**, 139.
7. G. H. CAREY and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 2859.
8. S. N. LIMAYE and M. C. SAXENA, *Pro. Natl. Acad. Sci. India, Sect. A*, 1986, **56**, 292.
9. R. J. MOTEKAITIS and A. E. MARTELL, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1982, **60**, 2403.
10. H. SIGEL, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1975, **14**, 394; *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 1535.
11. L. C. THOMPSON and J. A. LORASS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 89.
12. F. J. C. ROSSOTTI, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", eds. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILLIAMS, Interscience, New York, 1967.
13. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VASIL'EV, "Instability Constants of Complex Compounds", Pergamon, New York, 1960.
14. T. POI and G. H. NANCOLLAS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 2414.
15. G. DEGISCHER and G. H. NANCOLLAS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 1125.
16. D. R. PARRY and C. D. S. TOMLIN, Ger. Pat., 2337 289/1974 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, **80**, 108852).
17. R. N. K. VISHWANATHAM, K. RAM and M. G. R. REDDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 270.
18. R. N. K. VISHWANATHAM and M. G. R. REDDY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 856.
19. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3397, 2904.
20. A. E. MARTELL and W. CHABEREK, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1477.
21. S. RAMAMOORTHY and M. SANTAPPA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 1623; *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 38.

